

Product catalogue

Glucosamine, Chitosan, Chitosan Derivatives, Chitosan Oligosaccharide

CD Bioparticles
Drug Delivery

About Us

CD Bioparticles is an established drug delivery company which provides customized solutions for developing and producing new, biocompatible drug delivery systems.

CD Bioparticles has production workshops and a quality control laboratory for Glucosamine, Chitosan, Chitosan Oligosaccharide, Chitin Derivatives etc, which are widely used in food, medicine, cosmetic, agricultural seeds, daily chemicals, industrial wastewater treatment and other industries. Dedicated workshops are all in full compliance with domestic and international GMP requirements.

Today we offer you:

A fully certified high-quality chitosan. This is an excellent choice for your chitosan supply if you seek to translate your chitosan R&D to commercialization:

- Chitosan (Industrial Grade, Food Grade, Medical Grade, High Density)
- Most of the chitosan is extracted from crab and shrimp shells; We also have Mushroom Chitosan made from natural agaricus bisporus, and oyster mushroom.
- Providing GMP grade Chitosan or Chitosan derivatives and bulk orders via custom synthesis, offering the opportunity to match customers' special quality requirements

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CAS number: 9012-76-4

Chitosan Series are supplied as off-white or slight yellow powder. It is soluble in acid, and insoluble in water, base or normal organic solutions. Chitosan Series are widely used in the pharmaceutical industry, food industry and light industry. In particular, chitosan can stabilize the composition of drugs as a drug carrier. It can promote the absorption, delay or control the dissolution rate and help drugs to reach the target organs. Besides, it is anti-acid, anti-ulcer, and can also prevent drugs from stimulating the stomach.

Catalog No	Name	Viscosity	Unit Size
CSGN003	Clnd™ Chitosan (Medical Grade)	10-800 mpa.s	1 kg, 25 kg
CSGN004	Clnd™ Chitosan (Special Molecular Weight)	--	1 kg, 25kg
CSGN005	Clnd™ Chitosan (Industrial Grade)	50-800 mpa.s	1 kg, 25 kg
CSGN008	Clnd™ Chitosan (Food Grade)	50-800 mpa.s	1 kg, 25 kg
CSGN012	Clnd™ Chitosan (High-density)	50-800 mpa.s	1 kg, 25 kg

CAS number: 148411-57-8

Chitosan Oligosaccharide Series are supplied as yellow powder with good water solubility. Chitosan Oligosaccharide can be directly used for dairy products and condiments. In Agriculture, chitosan oligosaccharide can be developed for biological pesticide, growth regulator and fertilizers, etc. In addition, chitosan oligosaccharides have obvious moisturizing effects. It can be used in moisturizing, anti-wrinkle, sunscreen and other skin care products.

Catalog No	Name	MW	Unit Size
CSGN013	CInd™ Chitosan Oligosaccharide (Food Grade)	≤ 2 kDa	1 kg
CSGN014	CInd™ Chitosan Oligosaccharide (Agricultural Grade)	≤ 3 kDa	1 kg
CSGN015	CInd™ Chitosan Oligosaccharide (Cosmetic Grade)	≤ 2 kDa	1 kg

CAS number: 83512-85-0 (CSGN016, CSGN017); 70694-72-3 (CSGN021, CSGN022); not available (CSGN018, CSGN019, CSGN020, CSGN023, CSGN024, CSGN025, CSGN026, CSGN027)

Water-Soluble Chitosan is mostly supplied as white or off-white powder, soluble in water and stable. Water-Soluble Chitosan has good biocompatibility, film-forming property and excellent antibacterial property, that can be used as cosmetics, cosmetic raw materials, food additives or preservatives, etc. It also has health care function for being dissolved and absorbed well. It is made into capsule health care products, which is convenient to take.

Catalog No	Name	Viscosity	Unit Size
CSGN016	Clnd™ Carboxymethyl Chitosan	≤100 mpa.s	1 kg, 25 kg
CSGN017	Clnd™ Carboxymethyl Chitosan (Medical Grade)	≤100 mpa.s	1 kg, 25 kg
CSGN018	Clnd™ N-Carboxy Propionyl Chitosan Sodium (CPCTS)	--	1 kg, 25 kg
CSGN019	Clnd™ N-Carboxy Propionyl Chitosan Sodium (CPCTS) (Medical Standard of Tissue Engineering)	5-30 mpa.s	1 kg, 25 kg
CSGN020	Clnd™ Analogous Hyaluronic Acid Chitosan	--	1 kg, 25 kg
CSGN021	Clnd™ Chitosan Hydrochloride	--	5 kg, 10 kg
CSGN022	Clnd™ Chitosan Hydrochloride (Medical Standard of Tissue Engineering)	--	1 kg, 25 kg
CSGN023	Clnd™ Chitosan Nitrate	< 200 mpa.s	1 kg, 2 kg
CSGN024	Clnd™ Chitosan Azelate	< 200 mpa.s	1 kg, 2 kg
CSGN025	Clnd™ Chitosan Lactate	< 200 mpa.s	1 kg, 2 kg
CSGN026	Clnd™ Chitosan Quaternary Ammonium Salt	--	1 kg, 25 kg
CSGN027	Clnd™ Water Soluble Chitosan Qlutamate	≤200 mpa.s	1 kg, 25 kg

CAS number: 9012-76-4

Plant-based non-animal Chitosan uses chitosan only from Agaricus Bisporus Mushroom and Aspergillus Niger, such as oyster and white button mushroom, 100% naturally non-animal sourced (Mushroom/Aspergillus Niger). Plant-based Non-animal Chitosan contains beta-glucan, but crustacean chitosan not. Mushroom/Aspergillus Niger chitosan is suitable for a wide variety of dietary restrictions. This includes vegan, kosher, and halal diets and most importantly it does not contain allergens, making it safe for everyone.

Microbiological Quality:

Total Plate Count	Yeast and Mold	E.Coli	Salmonella
≤1000cfu/g	≤100cfu/g	Negative	Negative

Catalog No	Name	Description	Unit Size
CSVB001	Mushroom Chitosan, 20-100 cps	Acid Soluble; DDA 85%-98%	1 kg
CSVB002	Mushroom Chitosan, 100-500 cps	Acid Soluble; DDA 85%-98%	1 kg
CSVB003	Mushroom Chitosan, 500-1000 cps	Acid Soluble; DDA 85%-98%	1 kg
CSVB004	Water Soluble Mushroom Chitosan, Hydrochloride	Water Soluble; Viscosity 20cps; DDA 90%-98%	1 kg
CSVB005	Mushroom Chitosan, Oligosaccharide	Water Soluble; MW<3000 Da	1 kg
CSVB006	Aspergillus Niger Chitsosan	Acid Soluble; DDA 85%-98%; Viscosity > 15 cps	1 kg
CSVB007	Aspergillus Niger Chitsosan, Hydrochloride	Water Soluble; Viscosity 15-50 cps	1 kg
CSVB008	Aspergillus Niger Chitsosan, Oligosaccharide	Water Soluble; MW<3000 Da	1 kg
CSVB009	High/Regular Density Aspergillus Niger Chitsosan	High Density>0.7 g/mL	1 kg
CSVB010	Mushroom Carboxymethyl Chitosan	Water Soluble; Viscosity 10-80 cps; Degree of Substitution 0.8	1 kg

CAS number: 7512-17-6 (CSGN006); 66-84-2 (CSGN007); 31284-96-5 (CSGN010)

D-Glucosamine Series are supplied as white powder. D-Glucosamine Series can be used to suppress cancer cells and treat osteoarthritis in the medical field. Also, it can be used as food preservatives and additives. The spectral data of D-Glucosamine series is shown in the below table.

Microbiological Quality:

Total Plate Count ≤1000cfu/g	Yeast and Mold ≤100cfu/g	E.Coli Negative	Staphylococcus Aureus Negative	Salmonella Negative
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Catalog No	Name	Content	Unit Size
CSGN006	CInd™ N-acetyl-D-Glucosamine	98.0%-102.0%	1 kg, 25 kg
CSGN007	CInd™ D-Glucosamine Hydrochloride	98.0%-102.0%	1 kg, 25 kg
CSGN010	CInd™ D-Glucosamine Sulfate-2KCl	98.0%-102.0%	1 kg, 25 kg

CAS number: 66-84-2 (CSGN002); 31284-96-5 (CSGN009); 38899-05-7 (CSGN011)

DC Series are supplied as a white grain, which are soluble in water, but insoluble in ordinary organic solvent such as ethanol, and faintly soluble in methanol. DC Series are based on D-Glucosamine Series using PVP K-30 or HPMC as excipient carrier for processing, and can be directly used for pharmaceutical tablet and capsule perfusion. DC Series also can be used in medicine and food. The spectral data of DC series is shown in the below table.

Microbiological Quality:

Total Plate Count	Yeast and Mold	E.Coli	Salmonella
≤1000cfu/g	≤100cfu/g	Negative	Negative

Catalog No	Name	Content	Unit Size
CSGN002	D-Glucosamine HCl (DC Grade)	≥ 95.0%	1 kg, 25 kg
CSGN009	D-Glucosamine Sulfate 2KCl (DC Grade)	≥ 95.0%	1 kg, 25 kg
CSGN011	D-Glucosamine Sulfate·2NaCl (DC Grade)	≥ 95.0%	1 kg, 25 kg

CAS number: 9082-07-9

Chondroitin Sulfate Sodium is supplied as white powder with strong water absorption. Chondroitin sulfate Sodium is an acidic mucopolysaccharide extracted from animal tissues. Major use of Chondroitin Sulfate Sodium in medicine is as a drug in the treatment of joint diseases. It is used together with glucosamine to reduce the pain of patients with osteoarthritis, promote cartilage regeneration, improve joint function, reduce joint swelling and effusion, prevent the space between knee joint and hand joint from narrowing, which can fundamentally improve joint problems.

Microbiological Quality:

Total Plate Count	Yeast and Mold	E.Coli	Salmonella
≤1000cfu/g	≤100cfu/g	Negative	Negative

Catalog No	Name	Content	Unit Size
CSGN030	Clnd™ Chondroitin Sulfate Sodium	499.38	1 kg, 25 kg

Contact Us

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